

Action of Hydrazides. Part I. Synthesis of Triazines from Aminoguanidine and Diketones.

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Semicarbazide reacts with most diketones so as to yield semicarbazones (Bromberg, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 132; Thiele and Barlow, *Annalen*, 1898, 302, 323; Schmidt and Sauer, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 276, 3250). With benzil, however, it forms a triazine derivative (Thiele and Stanger, *Annalen*, 1894, 283, 20).

In a study of the reaction between aminoguanidine and α -diketones, Thiele and Bihan (*Annalen*, 1898, 302, 307) found that the aliphatic α -diketones yield osazones, whilst benzil yields a derivative of triazine, thus:—

The author has studied further the reaction between aminoguanidine and aromatic diketones, and as a result derivatives of triazine have been obtained.

The behaviour of semicarbazide towards diketones is thus different from that of aminoguanidine. The most reasonable explanation for the tendency of aminoguanidine to form a ring system is, perhaps, its stronger basic character. In semicarbazide, $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$, which is the amide of hydrazocarbonic acid, $\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{COOH}$, the amino part of the group ($-\text{CO} \cdot \text{NH}_2$) is acidic in its nature. When the hydrazine residue combines with a ketonic group in a diketone so as to form a semicarbazone, the acidity of the amino group is enhanced, and this group is prevented from reacting with the remaining ketonic group, which also is acidic in nature. It would seem that a triazine might be formed, but it is not, by the elimination of a molecule of water from the semicarbazone. The triazine is formed, however, from the semicarbazone monoxime in

which the acidity of the $-\text{CO}$ group has been reduced by conversion into $-\text{C}:\text{NOH}$.

Aminoguanidine differs from semicarbazide in having an imino group in place of the oxygen atom of the $-\text{CO}$ group. Owing to the imino group, the amino group in the amidine residue, $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{NH}$, is basic, accordingly a hydrazone, formed by the condensation of aminoguanidine with a diketone, can part with a molecule of water and yield a triazine.

Thiele and Bihan (*loc. cit.*) have described a hydrazone derived from β -naphthoquinone and aminoguanidine, which with alkali gives β -naphthol and a compound, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}$.

On repeating their process the author has not found it possible to isolate the hydrazone. Thiele has not given the constitution of the compound, $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}$. From the behaviour of diphenylaminotriazine, phenanthro-aminotriazine and naphtho-aminotriazine it appears to the present author that under the influence of alkali a portion of the hydrazone decomposes giving β -naphthol, while another portion loses a molecule of water forming a naphtho-aminotriazine, the amino group of which is then replaced by a hydroxyl group forming a naphthohydroxytriazine. This view finds experimental support in that naphtho-aminotriazine has been prepared and converted into the above naphthohydroxytriazine.

The colour of the triazines obtained from aminoguanidine with benzil, phenanthraquinone, acenaphthenequinone and isatin is yellow and that with β -naphthoquinone red. Contrary to expectation the colour of the triazines in the phenanthraquinone series could not be deepened by introducing bromine or the nitro group. The colour of the triazines is diminished by acetylation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

5:6-Acenaphtho-3-aminotriazine.

To acenaphthenequinone in hot acetic acid solution was added the requisite quantity of aminoguanidine hydrochloride and the mixture boiled for three hours. The aminotriazine was precipitated with ammonia as a yellowish brown flocculent precipitate which after crystallisation from pyridine was obtained in deep yellow shining plates, m. p. above 305°. It is insoluble in water, benzene, ether and alcohol. (Found :N, 25·63. $C_{13}H_8N_4$ requires N, 25·45 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from alcohol in feebly yellow needles, m. p. 268°. (Found :N, 21·61. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_4$ requires N, 21·37 per cent.).

5:6-Naphtho-3-aminotriazine.

β -Naphthoquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride in acetic acid solution were heated for four hours after which the triazine was precipitated with ammonia as a red amorphous powder. This was collected and crystallised from pyridine in reddish yellow microscopic needles, m. p. 240°. It is insoluble in water, benzene, and ether; very slightly soluble in alcohol. (Found :N, 28·80. $C_{13}H_8N_4$ requires N, 28·57 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was obtained as a dirty white precipitate, m. p. 208°, insoluble in ordinary organic solvents. (Found :N, 23·32. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_4$ requires N, 23·53 per cent.).

5:6-Naphtho-3-hydroxytriazine.

It was obtained from aminonaphthotriazine with strong potassium hydroxide solution. As the triazine decomposed it gradually went

into solution and after several hours' heating, a small quantity of a yellow precipitate separated which, however, dissolved in the alkaline solution on dilution with water. From this solution the free base was precipitated with acid as a yellow powder which crystallised from alcohol in yellow micro-crystalline powder. It dissolves in alcohol with a red colour and green fluorescence. It is insoluble in benzene, chloroform and ether; soluble in alcohol and acetic acid. (Found: N, 21.45. $C_{11}H_7ON_3$ requires N, 21.32 per cent.). Thiele and Barlow (*loc. cit.*) probably obtained this compound by heating β -naphthoquinone aminoguanidine with a concentrated aqueous solution of alkali and the pronounced acid character of the substance, noticed by them, is due to the presence of a phenolic group in the molecule.

5:6-Isato-3-aminotriazine.

Molecular quantities of isatin and aminoguanidine hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution. At first the solution was red and as the reaction proceeded it assumed an orange colour and after a few minutes long needles of the hydrochloride of amino-isato-triazine began to separate. After an hour the mixture was allowed to cool when a further quantity of crystals was deposited. The hydrochloride was dissolved in water and the triazine precipitated with ammonia as yellow needles. Crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles it turned brown at 200° and did not melt at 296° . (Found: N, 37.99. $C_9H_7N_3$ requires N, 37.84 per cent.).

The acetyl derivative separated from alcohol in light yellow microscopic crystals, m.p. 200° . (Found: N, 25.85. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 26.02 per cent.).

5:6-Bromophenanthro-3-aminotriazine.

It was obtained from 2-bromophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride in acetic acid solution, precipitating with ammonia. Crystallised from alcohol it was obtained in reddish yellow needles, m.p. 235° . It is insoluble in benzene and chloroform;

soluble in acetic acid and pyridine. (Found: N, 17.59. $C_{11}H_8N_4Br$ requires N, 17.23 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative was purified by crystallisation from pyridine from which it separated in light yellow microscopic crystals, m.p. 278°. (Found: N, 15.48. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_4Br$ requires N, 15.26 per cent.).

5:6-Dibromophenanthro-3-aminotriazine, prepared from 4:5-dibromophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride as described before, crystallised from pyridine in greenish yellow plates which did not melt at 305°. It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene and chloroform; very sparingly soluble in acetic acid. (Found: N, 14.13. $C_{11}H_8N_4Br_2$ requires N, 13.86 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from nitrobenzene in light yellow rectangles not melting at 310°. It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene, acetic acid and pyridine. (Found: N, 12.68. $C_{17}H_{10}ON_4Br_2$ requires N, 12.56 per cent.).

5:6-Dibromo-phenanthro-3-aminotriazine.—It was prepared from 2:7-dibromophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride by methods already described. The precipitate that separated was collected and crystallised from pyridine when it formed orange coloured rectangles, m.p. 288°. It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene and chloroform; very slightly soluble in acetic acid but readily in hot pyridine. (Found: N, 14.08. $C_{11}H_8N_4Br_2$ requires N, 13.86 per cent.).

5:6-Nitrophenanthro-3-aminotriazine.—2-Nitrophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride were heated in acetic acid solution as before and the triazine was precipitated with ammonia. This was collected and crystallised from pyridine yellow needles with a greenish tinge, m.p. 280°. It is insoluble in alcohol, chloroform and benzene and almost insoluble in acetic acid. (Found: N, 24.37. $C_{13}H_9O_2N_5$ requires N, 24.05 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from pyridine in light yellow needles which turned brown at 280° and melted at 298°. (Found: N, 21.30. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N_5$ requires N, 21.02 per cent.).

5:6-Nitrophenanthro-3-aminotriazine.—It was prepared from 4-nitrophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride. The acid solution was diluted with water and the base was precipitated with alkali as a yellow crystalline mass. This was obtained pure from acetic acid from which it separated in yellow needles, m. p. 215°. (Found: N, 24.31. $C_{13}H_9O_2N_5$ requires N, 24.05 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow rectangles or needles, m.p. 270°. (Found: N, 21.25. $C_{17}H_{10}O_4N_6$ requires N, 21.02 per cent.).

5:6-Dinitrophenanthro-3-aminotriazine.—It was prepared from 2:7-dinitrophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride in presence of acetic acid. The base precipitated with alkali was purified from nitrobenzene from which it crystallised in needles of brown colour which did not melt at 310°. It is insoluble in alcohol benzene and chloroform; very slightly soluble in pyridine. (Found: N, 25.25. $C_{17}H_8O_4N_6$ requires N, 25.0 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from pyridine in light yellow needles which did not melt at 310°. (Found: N, 22.46. $C_{17}H_{10}O_4N_6$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.).

5:6-Dinitrophenanthro-8-aminotriazine.—It was obtained from 4:5-dinitrophenanthraquinone and aminoguanidine hydrochloride in acetic acid solution. The dirty yellow precipitate was purified by crystallisation from pyridine in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 265°. It is insoluble in benzene, chloroform, alcohol and acetic acid; soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. (Found: N, 25.38. $C_{17}H_8O_4N_6$ requires N, 25.00 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative crystallised from pyridine in straw yellow rectangles, m.p. 275°. (Found: N, 22.28. $C_{17}H_{10}O_4N_6$ requires N, 22.22 per cent.).

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